

Synthesis of Steroidal Aminopyrimidines

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Steroidal derivatives with fused pyrimidine ring system have been found to possess a variety of pharmacological and biological activities¹. Hence, it was thought of interest to undertake the synthesis of steroidal pyrimidines of androstane series.

The synthesis of substituted pyrimidines from α,β -unsaturated ketones was reported². Presently, we have investigated condensation of steroidal chalcones with guanidine hydrochloride to see if the corresponding pyrimidines can be obtained by this approach. 3β -Substituted-androst-5-en-17-one (**1**)³ on base-catalysed reaction with various aromatic

aldehydes, such as benzaldehyde, *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde, *p*-methylbenzaldehyde, *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde and *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde in ethanolic solution gave the respective chalcones, 3β -substituted-16-arylidene-androst-5-en-17-one (**2a-j**) (Table 1).

The chalcones (**2a-j**) were condensed with guanidine hydrochloride in presence of base to furnish 2'-amino-6'-aryl-5-androsteno[17,16-*d*]-pyrimidines (**3a-j**). The structures of steroidal 2-aminopyrimidines (**3a-j**) were confirmed by pmr which showed D₂O exchangeable broad singlet at δ 5.7 for

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS **2***

Compd. no.	R	Ar	Yield %	M.p °C	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹		δ				
					Ester CO	Ketone CO	Benzylidene-H (s)	Steroidal C ₆ -H (m)	Steroidal C ₃ α -H (m)	OAc (s)	ArMe or ArOMe (s)
2a	OAc	Ph	82	192	1 735	1 710	6.75	5.45	4 65	2 10	
b	OAc	C ₆ H ₄ OMe- <i>p</i>	83	214	1 735	1 710	6.74	5.48	4 62	2.18	3.42
c	OAc	C ₆ H ₄ Me- <i>p</i>	83	152	1 730	1 710	6.74	5.45	4 56	2.15	2 34
d	OAc	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ - <i>p</i>	80	209	1 730	1 715	6 74	5.45	4 56	2.10	—
e	OAc	C ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>p</i>	80	196	1 730	1 710	6.74	5.45	4 56	2 15	
f	Cl	Ph	78	178	—	1 710	6.70	5.48	4 60	—	—
g	Cl	C ₆ H ₄ OMe- <i>p</i>	80	222	—	1 710	6.65	5.45	4.55	—	3 40
h	Cl	C ₆ H ₄ Me- <i>p</i>	80	161	—	1 710	6 68	5.38	4 50	—	2 36
i	Cl	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ - <i>p</i>	76	152	—	1 710	6 65	5 45	4.60	—	—
j	Cl	C ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>p</i>	76	188	—	1 710	6.74	5.45	4 56	—	—

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

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TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Compd. no.	R	Ar	Yield %	M. p °C	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹		δ				
					NH ₂	CO	NH ₂ (bs)	Steroidal C ₆ -H (m)	Steroidal C ₃ α -H (m)	OAc (s)	ArMe or ArOMe (s)
3a	OAc	Ph	77	242	3 380	1 730	5.70	5.43	4.56	2.18	—
b	OAc	C ₆ H ₄ OMe- <i>p</i>	78	288	3 360	1 735	5.74	5.45	4.45	2.15	3.45
c	OAc	C ₆ H ₄ Me- <i>p</i>	78	226	3 380	1 730	5.78	5.48	4.50	2.10	2.38
d	OAc	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ - <i>p</i>	76	254	3 360	1 740	5.78	5.35	4.50	2.18	—
e	OAc	C ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>p</i>	75	238	3 370	1 730	5.76	5.38	4.52	2.15	—
f	Cl	Ph	73	228	3 360	—	5.74	5.45	4.50	—	—
g	Cl	C ₆ H ₄ OMe- <i>p</i>	74	260	3 380	—	5.78	5.35	4.48	—	3.42
h	Cl	C ₆ H ₄ Me- <i>p</i>	73	214	3 400	—	5.78	5.40	4.45	—	2.34
i	Cl	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ - <i>p</i>	70	240	3 380	—	5.75	5.38	4.50	—	—
j	Cl	C ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>p</i>	70	233	3 370	—	5.75	5.42	4.45	—	—

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

NH₂ protons and absence of signal at δ 6.7 for benzyldiene proton (Table 2).

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a JEOL FX-90 Q FT instrument with TMS as internal standard.

Chalcones (2a-j): To a solution of the ketone (1, 2 g) in ethanol (50 ml) were added aromatic aldehyde (1.5 g) and ethanolic solution of KOH (6 g KOH in 15 ml ethanol) at 0–5° and the reaction mixture was kept for 24 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then acidified with acetic acid (5 ml) and poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol (2.1 g). The compounds were found to be homogeneous on tlc (benzene-acetone, 9 : 1).

R = AcO and Cl

Ar = Ph, C₆H₄OMe-*p*, C₆H₄Me-*p*, C₆H₄NO₂-*p*, C₆H₄Cl-*p*

Chart 1

Aminopyrimidines (3a-j): To a solution of guanidine hydrochloride (0.5 g) in ethanol (10 ml) was added sodium hydroxide (0.25 g) and the solution was stirred for 15 min. The precipitated sodium chloride was filtered and the filtrate was added to a solution of the chalcone (2 ; 1 g) in ethanol (50 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h. The excess of solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residual solution was poured into ice-cold water. The resulting pale yellow solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from methanol.

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